

Kinetics of oxidation of glycine by pyridinium bromochromate in acetic acid medium

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Kinetics of oxidation of glycine by pyridinium bromochromate (PBC) have been studied in aquo-acetic acid medium in presence of perchloric acid. The products are ammonia, CO₂ and formaldehyde. The reaction shows first order kinetics in [PBC], inverse order with respect to [H⁺] and Michaelis-Meten type kinetics with respect to [glycine]. The rate of oxidation decreases with increase in dielectric constant of solvent indicating ion-dipole interaction. Activation parameters have been evaluated. Mechanism involving C-C fission has been suggested.

Kinetics of oxidation of benzhydrol¹, methionine², oxalic acid and formic acid³, aliphatic aldehydes⁴, benzyl alcohol⁵, aliphatic alcohol⁶ and thioacids⁷ by pyridinium bromochromate (PBC)⁸ are documented. Sharma *et al.*² proposed catalysis by H⁺ in oxidation of amino acids by PBC, but preliminary studies in our laboratory have shown contradictory results. The present investigation reports oxidation of amino acid (glycine) by PBC in acetic acid-water medium.

Results and Discussion

Effect of oxidant : At fixed [H⁺] with glycine in excess, plot log [PBC] against time is linear indicating first order in [PBC]. The first order rate constants are independent of initial concentration of PBC (Table 1).

Table 1. Variation of rate with oxidant concentration

[HClO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [Glycine] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, acetic acid = 30% (v/v), temp. = 303 K

10 ³ [PBC] (mol dm ⁻³)	1.60	2.00	2.50	3.30	5.00	7.00	9.00
10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	6.20	6.26	6.18	6.20	6.18	6.20	6.20

Effect of substrate : The rate of oxidation increases with increase in concentration of glycine (Table 2). Plot of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[glycine] gives straight line, which does not pass

Table 2. Variation of rate with glycine concentration

[HClO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [PBC] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, acetic acid = 30% (v/v), temp. = 303 K

10 ² [Glycine] (mol dm ⁻³)	1.25	1.66	2.00	3.30	5.00
10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	4.30	5.13	6.23	10.23	13.70

K_m = 10.28 × 10⁻³

through origin indicating Michaelis-Menten type kinetics. This indicates a complex formation between glycine and PBC.

Effect of perchloric acid : Rate of reaction decreases with increase in perchloric acid concentration (Table 3). This suggests that H⁺ ions react with glycine and form a non-reactive species. Plots of k_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺] and log k_{obs} vs log [H⁺] are also straight lines with slope ≈ 1, indicating an inverse first order dependence on [H⁺].

Table 3. Variation of rate with perchloric acid concentration

[Glycine] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [PBC] = 2 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, acetic acid = 30% (v/v), temp. = 303 K

10 ¹ [HClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	2.00	3.00	5.00	7.00	10.00	15.00
10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	25.70	18.23	15.38	8.82	6.14	4.93

Effect of ionic strength : Rate does not depend on concentration of sodium sulfate (Table 4) in the medium, indicating interactions in rate-determining step are not of ion-ion type.

Table 4. Variation of rate with sodium sulfate concentration

[HClO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [Glycine] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [PBC] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, acetic acid = 30% (v/v), temp. = 303 K

10 ² [Na ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	7.00	5.00	3.33	2.00	1.42	1.00
10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	6.20	6.22	6.24	6.20	6.18	6.20

Effect of solvent composition : At fixed ionic strength and [H⁺], the rate of oxidation of glycine with PBC increases with decrease in polarity of solvent. In other words, a decrease in rate with increase in dielectric constant is observed. This is due to polar character of the transition state as compared to the reactants. The plot of log k_{obs} vs 1/D

(dielectric constant) is linear with positive slope (= 66.7) indicating ion-dipole type of interaction⁹.

Effect of pyridine : There is no effect of addition of pyridine on rate of reaction, indicating that PBC is not hydrolyzed in the reaction. Further, this indicates stability of PBC during the reaction.

Effect of temperature : Rate of reaction increases with increase in temperature (Table 5). The log k_{obs} vs $1/T$ plot is a straight line in the temperature range 303–323 K. This shows that Arrhenius equation is valid in this case. The value of activation energy (ΔE_a^\ddagger) is 63.18 kJ mol⁻¹. The entropy value is negative and small, suggesting formation of a cyclic intermediate from non-cyclic species. It has been pointed out¹⁰ that if entropy of activation is negative and small, the reaction will be slow.

Table 5. Thermodynamic parameters

[HClO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [Glycine] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [PBC] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, acetic acid = 30% (v/v)

Temp. (K)	303	308	313	318	323
10 ⁵ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)	6.26	8.66	12.15	20.15	32.62

$\Delta S^\ddagger = 106.7 \pm 3.15$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, $\Delta E_a^\ddagger = 63.18 \pm 1.80$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta F^\ddagger = 95.31 \pm 2.92$ kJ mol⁻¹, pZ = 2.91 × 10⁷ s⁻¹ mol dm⁻¹

Scheme 1 explains all the observed experimental results.

Scheme 1

The over all reaction may be represented as

The rate law derived based on the above mechanism, is as follows :

$$\text{Rate of reaction} = -\frac{d[\text{C}]}{dt} \propto [\text{C}] \quad (2)$$

$$= k[\text{C}] \quad (3)$$

Concentration of complex, [C] can be calculated by applying steady state concept.

Rate of formation of complex = Rate of disappearance of complex

$$k_1' [\text{AA}][\text{PBC}]_{\text{eqm}} = k_{-1}' [\text{C}] + k [\text{C}] \quad (4)$$

where [AA] is equilibrium concentration.

$$\text{Since } [\text{PBC}]_{\text{total}} = [\text{PBC}]_{\text{eqm}} + [\text{C}] \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } [\text{PBC}]_{\text{eqm}} = [\text{PBC}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{C}]$$

Hence,

$$k_1' [\text{AA}]\{[\text{PBC}]_t - [\text{C}]\} = (k_{-1}' + k) [\text{C}]$$

$$k_1' [\text{AA}][\text{PBC}]_t - k_1' [\text{AA}] [\text{C}] = (k_{-1}' + k) [\text{C}]$$

$$\text{Therefore } \{k_{-1}' + k + k_1' [\text{AA}]\} [\text{C}] = k_1' [\text{AA}] [\text{PBC}]_t$$

Hence,

$$[\text{C}] = \frac{k_1' [\text{AA}] [\text{PBC}]_t}{k_{-1}' + k + k_1' [\text{AA}]}$$

$$= \frac{[\text{AA}] [\text{PBC}]_t}{\frac{k_{-1}' + k}{k_1'} + [\text{AA}]}$$

$$= \frac{[\text{AA}] [\text{PBC}]_t}{K_m + [\text{AA}]}$$

Hence,

$$\text{Rate} = k[\text{C}]$$

$$= k \frac{[\text{AA}] [\text{PBC}]_t}{K_m + [\text{AA}]}$$

$$= k_1 [\text{PBC}]_t = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{PBC}]_t$$

where

$$k_1 = k \frac{[\text{AA}]}{K_m + [\text{AA}]}$$

$$\frac{1}{k_1} = \frac{K_m}{k} \frac{1}{[AA]} + \frac{1}{k}$$

Therefore, K_m can be calculated by slope/intercept of plot $1/k_1$ vs $1/[AA]$.

This rate law explains all the observed results – decrease in rate of reaction can be explained based on eqn. (1), i.e. amino acid concentration will decrease as H^+ concentration increases and hence decrease in rate of reaction.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Purity of glycine was checked by m.p. PBC was prepared and its purity checked by the usual method⁸. Acetic acid was purified by reported method¹¹. The reaction was carried out under pseudo-first order condition in water-acetic acid containing $HClO_4$. The course of reaction was followed iodometrically. The rate constants computed from the linear plots of log (hypo) against time by least-square method were reproducible within $\pm 2\%$.

The qualitative product study was made under kinetic conditions. On completion of the reaction, reaction solution was neutralized by $NaHCO_3$ and extracted with ether. Ether layer was treated with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 1 *N* HCl to get hydrazone, then m.p. compared with authentic sample to confirm formaldehyde. Ammonium ion and CO_2 were detected by Nesslar's reagent and lime-water test, respectively.

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